

Psychological Contract, Symbolic Interactionism, Social Exchange, and Expectation Violation Theories: A Literature Review

Roberto Aylmer

Fundação Getulio Vargas, Brazil

Mariana Aylmer

Rennes School of Business, France

Murillo Dias

Fundação Getulio Vargas, Brazil

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Abstract:

This article presents a literature review on Symbolic Interactionism, Social Exchange, and Expectation Violation Theories and their relevance to the Psychological Contract. The review is part of a doctoral thesis on the socialization process and can be helpful to Human Resource Managers (HRM), scholars, and practitioners. The review's findings show that while there are many studies on the newcomer's adaptation in the international literature, there are very few academic studies on this topic in the Brazilian context where the cost of losing a job can induce a golden cage behavior as we see in the public sector companies. Therefore, the review provides a new

perspective on the socialization process of a firm's newcomer by combining the theories above, which have not been studied together before.

Keywords: *Psychological Contract, Symbolic Interactionism, Social Exchange, and Expectation Violation Theory.*

Introduction

This work is part of the doctoral thesis (Aylmer, 2019). In Organizational Socialization and the Profession of Management, the Socialization Process (SP) is one of the most challenging stages of professional life. It describes the stage as "when a newcomer learns the value system, the norms, and the required behavior patterns of the society, organization, or group he is entering" (Schein, 1968, p.3). In general, socializing has the connotation of becoming social and meeting in society. Simply put, it consists of a process that is related to learning and bringing together individuals and social groups in different contexts (Saks & Ashforth,

1997). From a broader organizational perspective, the SP aims to prepare newcomers to become influential members of an existing group, adapt to its norms and values, think, feel, and act in ways the group considers appropriate, becoming part of the group (Moreland & Levine, 1982, 2001; Persell, 1990; Black & Ashford, 1995; De Vos, Buyens, & Schalk, 2003; Myers & Oetzel, 2003; Myers & Sadaghiani, 2010; Van Maanen & Schein, 1977).

In other words, SP refers to the process by which an individual acquires the attitudes, behaviors, and knowledge required to be accepted and participate as an organizational member (Allen et al., 2017; Bauer & Erdogan,

2011; Bauer et al., 1998; Cable & Parsons, 2001; Van Maanen & Schein, 1979).

Although SP is a recurrent process in different career stages, the first experiences in a company convey more dramatic contours than the change of area in the same company (Bauer et al., 2007; Bauer & Erdogan, 2011; Wang et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2011).

Considering that the decision for the public sector is a long-term career strategy, newcomers may perceive it as a "life commitment" or a "life sentence," depending on the primal experiences; onboarding a newcomer is highly relevant for HRM in the BPS. These future opposite perspectives once solidified as beliefs, will drive many newcomers' behavior towards the company and the work itself, influencing the construction of organizational realities and the foundation for their situational identities. In organizational socialization studies, it is well-known that when newcomers are in probationary positions, socialization encompasses high-stakes and high-stress situations (Bauer & Truxillo, 2000; Van Maanen & Schein, 1979), abounding with shocks and surprises (Kim et al., 2005), arising a high level of anxiety (Katz, 1985). Theoretically, the probationary period in the Brazilian public sector includes the first three years after admittance. However, very rarely is someone dismissed, and no mention of this threat has been made in contact with employees or is mentioned in the literature studied. However, appropriate management of the initial period in the company tends to decrease unnecessary suffering considerably, channeling talents and energies to the company's goals rather than deviating energies to deal with anxiety and perceived threats (Allen et al., 2017).

Most of the literature cited above refers to the newcomer's adaptation to the new workplace. However, the present context urges for a broader perspective, as approached by the Psychological Contract Theory (PC), via the individual's perception of the reciprocal obligations that underlie the exchange relationship between the employee and the employer (Delobbe et al., 2016).

Our research takes a unique approach by focusing on the newcomers' perspective in understanding the socialization process in the Brazilian public sector. This is a departure from the majority of literature in Brazil, which primarily examines the organizational perspective and the employee's adaptation to the firm.

Thus, this work presents a literature review on Psychological Contract, Symbolic Interactionism, Social Exchange, and Expectation Violation Theories. Moreover, beyond the organizational or individual perspective, the ongoing social changes reshape organizations and the nature of work, challenging private and public sectors to review people management premises and practices (Alcover et al., 2017; Cascio & Aguinis, 2008). The symbolic interactionism theory (SIT), social exchange theory (SET), and expectancy violation theory (EVT), which approach the construction of the psychological contract (PC), are helpful in better understanding the socialization process for the firms' newcomers.

Methodology

In this research, we modified our approach to developing the literature review by adjusting our steps and following an inductive and interpretive rationale based on the current epistemology of the topics investigated.

Symbolic Interactionism Theory

Symbolic interactionism (Blumer, 1969; Berger & Luckmann, 1967) is the process of social interaction through which meaning, and identity arise. The underpinning of SIT is the construction of meaning through the actor's (i.e. the person under study) interaction with the world (Aksan, et al., 2009), thus, SIT is the process through which newcomers establish situational identities (Katz, 1980; Wanous, 1992) and make sense of organizational realities, events, practices, and procedures (Reichers, 1987), in other words, SIT is suggested as the

process through which newcomers are socialized.

SIT authors affirm that the source of data is human interaction, and the core subjects of symbolic interaction are these relational perspectives, consequently, meaning results from the relationship between an act, the response to that act by someone else, and the result of that interaction (Blumer, 1969) and empathy is key for developing participants' abilities (Berg, 2001).

For the sake of our study is pivotal to understand the importance of newcomers' perception, independently if their interpretation is accurate or not, because a fact is created by an individual's perception, and it changes in time (Berg, 2001).

The creation of meaning in newcomers-insiders interaction is important to understand the how newcomers construct meaning confronting expectancies and experiences and probing the exchanges among parties in a cost-benefit perspective, comparing alternatives and defining outcomes.

Social Exchange Theory

Social Exchange provides a theoretical keystone of research on work attitudes and behaviors (Settoon, Bennett, & Liden, 1996; Wayne, Shore, & Liden, 1997), Distinct from the economic exchange, social exchange relationships implicate voluntary behaviors that create future obligations and have to be left to the discretion of the other party (Blau, 1964) investing in the relationship.

Social exchange authors (Blau, 1964; Homans, 1961; Rupp & Cropanzano, 2002; Wayne, et al., 1997) advocated that employees form a distinct relationship with the organization depending on how they are treated by incumbents; premise also supported by Gouldner (1960) as the norm of reciprocity.

Newcomers-incumbents exchanges are influenced by the Perceived Organizational Support (POS), that includes the relationship with supervisors (Graen & Scandura, 1987;

Henderson, Wayne, Shore, Bommer, & Tetrick, 2008; Bordia et al., 2010; Sparrowe & Liden 1997) also known as the leader-member exchange (LMX) (Khazanchi & Masterson, 2011; Tekleab & Chiaburu, 2011), and the team-member exchange (TMX) that is the relationship between the newcomer and members of the workgroup (Seers, 1989).

POS represents employees' presumption of the degree their contributions are valued; therefore, the organization will take care of their well-being, providing material and emotional support when they face stressful situations (George, Reed, Ballard, Collin, & Fielding, 1993) In turn, employees feel compelled to reciprocate by taking actions of equivalent value (Gouldner, 1960; Wayne et al., 1997).

High level of POS influences employees' commitment to their organization (Masterson, Lewis, Goldman, & Taylor, 2000) and their engagement with the job (Cropanzano, Howes, Grandey, & Toth, 1997). It also encourages employees to reciprocate through valued and desirable behaviors (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002; Wayne et al., 1997).

Depicting the concept of LMX and TMX in the workplace, LMX refers to the extent to which employees perceive high-quality exchange in dyadic relationships with their supervisors (Graen & Scandura, 1987; Wayne et al., 1997) and TMX, the differentiated exchange with peers (Van Dick, Van Knippenberg, Kerschreiter, Hertel, & Wieseke, 2008; Van Knippenberg & Van Schie, 2000).

A supervisor has twofold roles in the LMX relationship, to know (a) the supervisor-employee's exchange, in which the supervisor's attitudes fulfill or not the employee's expectancies but also (b) a role as a representative of the organization in the employee-organization exchange, becoming the voice of the organization for the newcomer. High-quality LMX relationships foster employees' autonomy, increasing collaboration and information sharing (Graen & Uhl-Bien, 1995; Graen & Scandura, 1987; Sparrowe & Liden 1997). High-quality LMX has also been related to increase risk-taking and performance

(Tierney, Farmer, & Graen, 1999). In few words, when newcomers perceive a high-quality LMX, they presume that the organization is fulfilling its part of the mutual obligation and tend to reciprocate (De Vos et al., 2003).

Regarding TMX, relationships with peers are a significant channel for attaining role-related and organizational knowledge (Jokisaari & Nurmi, 2009) reciprocity and consist of a social exchange where "each party must offer something the other sees as valuable, and each must see the exchange as reasonably equitable and fair" (Graen & Scandura, 1987, p.182).

LMX and TMX have been considered, for many authors as determinants of newcomers' adjustment (Jokisaari & Nurmi, 2009; Kammeyer-Mueller, Wanberg, Rubenstein, Song, 2013; Ostroff & Kozlowski, 1992; Reichers, 1987). They are of great importance to comprehend the dynamic of the socialization process (Madlock, 2008; Moideenkutty, Blau, Kumar, & Nalakath, 2001; Sluss & Thompson, 2012) and the construction of the psychological contract as well (Rousseau; 1989).

Psychological Contract

Very much intertwined with the concept of POS is the Psychological Contract (PC). The seminal work of Denise Rousseau (1989), organizing previous work (e.g. Menninger, 1958; Argyris, 1960) proposed the Psychological Contract (PC) as the individual's perception of the reciprocal obligations which underlie the exchange relationship between the employee and the employer (Rousseau, 1989). Levinson's defined PC as "a series of mutual expectations which the parties to the relationship may not be aware of, but which govern relations with each other" (Levinson, Lipkin, & Meshkov, 1963, p. 21) expresses that an *unaware force may govern newcomers and incumbents' relationship*.

According to Hiltrop (1996), PC defines the employment relationship between the parties and frame the mutual expectancies that influence behavior. Therefore, PC may anticipate the kind of contributions employers will receive from employees and the type of compensation or

benefits employees will receive in return from the organization. Employees and employers tend to uphold a fair equilibrium of the mutual obligations and rewards they offer each other (Rousseau, 2004; Taylor & Tekleab, 2004).

Simply put, the PC constitutes an unspoken exchange agreement between employees and the organization that holds what employees believe they have been promised by the organization and what they believe they are required to give in return (Dabos & Rousseau, 2004; Janssens, Sels, & Van den Brande, 2003; Parzefall, 2008; Rousseau, 1995; Rousseau, 2001).

Differently from other authors, Payne et al. (2008) suggested that employees' psychological contract has its origins yet before admittance when still-candidates-for-the-job look after organizations that will fit their expectations. Expectations can be, for instance, part of an organization with a positive reputation, or join a company that offers attractive incentives, such as job stability, career fast-track growth, professional status, or attractive benefits (Rousseau, 1995).

However, pre-admittance expectations may be imprecise (Mohamed, Orife, & Slack, 2001) and not related to post admittance experiences, creating expectancies breaches as seen in the interviews' reports at Petrobras.

The company locus of our study is the major Brazilian company, top player at the sophisticated O&G industry in Latin America, and world leader in pre-salt deep waters technologies. Thus, it is plausible to consider that the OR elevates newcomers' expectancies to the highest. However, contrasting with this, there is a constant mention of "reality shock after entrance" along the research interviews that, clearly, influenced the PC development. This contrast will be approached by the expectancy violation theory (EVT).

Expectancy Violation Theory

The *expectancy violation theory* (EVT) helps to understand how preconceived ideas influence relationships since the first interactions,

triggering a sequence of reactions and, somehow, interfering with newcomers' adjustment. These concepts highlight the need of paying close attention to the socialization process, in an effort for reducing or buffering these expectations clashes, mostly in the BPS where a long tenure is the rule.

Expectancy is present in most theories around human interaction (Burgoon & Walter, 1990) and is defined as a stable pattern of behavior anticipation one holds regarding the other part (Cappella & Greene, 1982). Behavior anticipation is an evolutionary strategy to avoid from noxious persons and to approach those who appear valuable to associate with (Jones, 1986).

This previously fixed perception is also known as a *stereotype*, “a cognitive structure that contains the perceiver’s knowledge, beliefs, and expectations about a human group” (Hamilton & Trolie, 1986, p. 133). Thus, individuals are judged based on beliefs and contextual norms about appropriate behaviors in given circumstances. When a newcomer violates the expectations of what is perceived as *appropriate behavior*, it causes the violator to be judged negatively, influencing the perception regarding the relationship (Burgoon, 1993; Burgoon et al., 2000; Leets, 2001; Myers & Sadaghiani, 2010).

In few words, EVT posits that stereotypes provide information about individual's characteristics and are valued upon contextual norms that silently rule what is appropriate or not for a group (Burgoon, 1993; Burgoon et al., 2000).

In the case of our study, expectations' clash is the underpinning issue of the socialization process in the BPS. From the newcomer's perspective, there is an expectancy to join the company after a long journey of investing time and money in specific studies to win over the one of the most disputed public contests.

On the other side, there are older incumbents, holder of a hierarchical company's culture (Alvesson & Willmott, 2002; Smola & Sutton, 2002) somewhat skeptical of the commitment and dedication of these new employees

(Collinson & Collinson, 1997; Raines, 2002) with a well-established routine, and overstretched by other priorities rather than receiving newcomers.

Petrobras is a semipublic company with approximately 85,000 employees at the time of conclusion of this study (Petrobras, 2018), under active Unions, has an important role in influencing the public sector. Petrobras, in the same way as most of the public sector companies in Brazil, is considered a hierarchical company, with clear status distinction and communication formalities. The expected stereotype of a newcomer is someone that will be obedient and willing to comply with incumbents' ways-of-working, likewise incumbents used to do when they arrived at the company many years before (Marston, 2007).

It might be uncomfortable for old-timers, usually in higher rank positions, to accept newcomers who do not share the same work ethic, doubting their commitment and dedication to the organization, dismissing them as selfish or lazy (Collinson & Collinson, 1997; Raines, 2002).

After these judgments are established, authors posited that supervisors tend to interact with newcomers with some level of discomfort, disrespect, or even distrust, threatening the socialization process (Myers & Sadaghiani, 2010).

Furthermore, based on the similarity-attraction theoretical model, individuals are attracted to cooperate and work with people with whom they share common attitudes, beliefs and values (Devendorf & Highhouse, 2008) and absolutely, that was not the situation in most of the cases studied at Petrobras.

Both newcomers and old-timers were unprepared for that encounter, and HR staff were not aware of the dimension of this gap, once there was no previous experience to calibrate it. However, how a company manages (or fails to manage) newcomers' initial interactions with old-timers sends clear indications about the organizational culture (Cable & Parsons, 2001).

The following section will provide information on the Study Context and the Company Background that will aid in outlining the major picture and newcomers' mindset.

Implications and Discussion

The socialization process is important on both ways, for the company to speed up newcomers' usefulness, connecting them to the new workplace, and, from newcomers' perspective, to reduce uncertainty regarding their future expressed by the first question one makes after entry: "will I fit (in) here?."

The present study uses a *multifoci* approach to the complex newcomers' socialization in the BPS, in which side-bets are extremely high, unusual for new employees in the private sector. Thus, the present study follows a narrative from newcomers' perspective in three stages, to know, (a) the high *pre-entry expectations*, inflated by the organizational reputation, named before as promised land as a place where all my needs will be fulfilled (b) the *reality shock* and the defining relationship with supervisor, considered as "bridge or barrier" with the subsidiary importance of peers, as an alternative route for socialization when supervisors are inattentive or unreceptive (barrier), and (c) the *outcomes*, or observed consequences of the aforesaid interactions.

Central and surprising in this study was the observation of *common mental disorders* (CMD), among almost all the interviewees. According to Goldberg and Huxley (1992), although CMD is not considered a classic psychiatric diagnosis, nevertheless it represents significant psychic suffering, affecting newcomers' relationships and compromising performance in daily activities. CMD is related as an important cause of work withdrawal and economic losses, being a potential substrate for the development of more severe disorders (Fiorotti et al., 2010) and includes symptoms as difficulty in concentrating and forgetfulness, insomnia, fatigue, irritability, feeling of inutility, constant anxiety, and somatic complaints as stomach and head aches, that

affect the performance of daily activities (Goldberg & Goodyer, 2014).

Although digging in the psychiatric elements that are present as outcome of dysfunctional socialization processes is not the focus of the present study, continuous suffering, beyond one's coping capabilities is a well-known cause for the burnout syndrome that conveys severe consequences for the organization as increasing in the turnover and absenteeism rates, reducing productivity and demanding a long and difficult treatment (Aronsson et al., 2017). These implications are also relevant because it can spark legal consequences, once Burnout syndrome is a work-related disease - ICD 11, QD 85, according to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2024).

According to Corley and Gioia (2011); Gioia and Pitre (1990), theory is a statement of concepts and their interrelationships that shows how and why a phenomenon occurs, therefore, a theoretical contribution should offer *original insight* into a phenomenon by advancing knowledge in a way that is considered to have *utility* or usefulness for some purpose, in other words, it must consider two dimensions (a) originality and (b) utility.

The strength of the OR, not evinced in the socialization literature, creates a context in which newcomers act as if they have no choice rather than staying in that company, "no matter what". This belief is enhanced by newcomers' relatives that consider job and payment stability as a prize that covers all the prices one has to pay. When after admittance the socialization experience brings unexpected strains the contrast with the high expectations will be perceived as a reality shock which, in many cases, evokes a strong desire to leave. However, the side-bets are too high and newcomers decide to stay despite their suffering, reflecting on the commitment, performance and satisfaction.

Therefore, sunk costs and side bets are important influencers in the Brazilian public sector' socialization process, leading newcomers to endure situations that, without such advantages, they would not handle.

This study provides a deeper understanding on job socialization *silent suffering*, once the newcomer has no one to complain in and outside the company. Inside the company, some of the interviewees revealed embarrassment to express the difficulties of adaptation and the psychological stress and pain with first experiences after admittance. Supervisors or peers don't realize the level of suffering one may be experiencing, among relatives and friends outside the company, it was muted by the glamour and the status of being approved in a public tender, that in Brazil is considered a motive of pride. Therefore, enduring beyond coping capabilities may lead to mental illness or CMD.

This study anticipates the need of a profound revision of SP in the Brazilian public sector, opening some avenues for future researches, contributing to the current conversation on newcomers' socialization with a critical redirection of existing views on phenomena (Conlon, 2002).

In sum, the present research advances previous work on newcomers' socialization, digging on seminal papers on the subject that explored the phenomenon via newcomer's unfavorable reactions to the employer's failure to fulfill perceived obligations (Delobbe et al., 2016; Dulac et al., 2008), the psychological contract developed even before admittance (Payne et al., 2008) and as a response to perceived employer inducements and employee contributions (Delobbe et al., 2016; De Vos & Freese, 2011).

This study extends previous works on newcomers in the socialization process in three ways. First, under the umbrella of symbolic interactionism theory (Aksan et al., 2009; Blumer, 1969, 1986; Carter & Fuller, 2015; Handberg et al., 2015) we approach the process of verbal and social interaction through which meaning, and identity arise guiding newcomers on the journey of understanding organizational realities and establishing their situational identities.

Second, from the social exchange theory (Blau, 1964; Coyle-Shapiro & Conway, 2004; Sluss & Thompson, 2012), we propose that newcomers

have a strong impact from the contrast of the organizational reputation and the organizational reality, influencing their psychological contract, represented by the metaphors of aiming a promised land and getting trapped in a golden cage. In this subject, we advance the studies on the importance of the dyadic relationship with supervisor (LMX) and, followed by peers (TMX).

Third, we investigate how newcomers' perceptions of their "moral" obligation to stay in the public sector – indirectly explain socialization undesired outcomes, namely work withdrawal, common mental disorders and eventually, burnout syndrome.

This approach explores different standpoints in tandem and offers an insider's perspective, allowing a profound, surprising and unconventional dive into phenomena as preconized by Mintzberg (2005), building a theoretical model that provides a better understanding or permits accurate predictions about the observational set (Dubin, 1978).

These discoveries have many ramifications for study in several domains, including (i) negotiations with governmental agents (Araujo, C.; Dias, M., 2022; Correa, Teles, Dias, M., 2022; Dias & Navarro, 2018); (ii) business mediation (Dias, M., 2018); (iii) retail business negotiations (Dias, M. et al., 2015; Dias, M. et al., 2015, 2014, 2012); (iv) industrial negotiations (Dias, M., Navarro and Valle, 2013, Dias, M., et al., 2014; Dias, M., et al., 2013; Dias, M., & Davila, 2018); (v) debt collection negotiations (Dias, M., 2019, 2019b; Dias, M. and Lopes, 2019); (vi) interbank negotiations (Dias, M.; Pereira, L; Vieira, P., 2022), for instance.

Limitations and Future Research

One limitation is that we relied upon only two sources to collect our data—Google Scholar and the EBSCO database. Future research could include more and different databases.

Conclusion

This research aims to address a vacuum in the existing literature by conducting a comprehensive literature review that explores the concepts of Psychological Contract, Symbolic Interactionism, Social Exchange, and Expectation Violation Theories. The outcome is a revised literature review that succinctly outlines the elements, behaviors, and instruments that have the potential to impact the socialization process of newly arrived individuals in organizations. With this comprehension, businesses might devise novel tactics to enhance online work and negotiations in this constantly evolving working setting.

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References

Aksan, N., Kısac, B., Aydın, M., & Demirbuken, S. (2009). Symbolic interaction theory. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 1(1), 902-904. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2009.01.160>

Alcover, C.M., Rico, R., Turnley, W.H., & Bolino, M.C. (2017). Understanding the changing nature of psychological contracts in 21st century organizations: A multiple-foci exchange relationships approach and proposed framework. *Organizational Psychology Review*, 7(1), 4-35. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2041386616628333>

Allen, D.G., & Shanock, L.R. (2013). Perceived organizational support and embeddedness as key mechanisms connecting socialization tactics to commitment and turnover among new employees. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*,

34(3), 350-369. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.1805>

Allen, N.J., & Meyer, J.P. (1990). The measurement and antecedents of affective, continuance and normative commitment to the organization. *Journal of occupational psychology*, 63(1), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8325.1990.tb00506.x>

Allen, N.J., & Meyer, J.P. (1993). Organizational Commitment: Evidence of Career Stage Effects? *Journal of Business Research*, 26(1), 49-61. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0148-2963\(93\)90042-N](https://doi.org/10.1016/0148-2963(93)90042-N)

Allen, T. D., Eby, L. T., Chao, G. T., & Bauer, T. N. (2017). Taking stock of two relational aspects of organizational life: Tracing the history and shaping the future of socialization and mentoring research. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 102(3), 324. <http://doi.org/10.1037/apl0000086>

Alvesson, M., & Willmott, H. (2002). Identity regulations as organizational control: Producing the appropriate individual. *Journal of Management Studies*, 39, 619-644. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-6486.00305>

Argyris, C. (1960). *Understanding organizational behavior*. London: Tavistock Publications.

Aronsson, G., Theorell, T., Grape, T., Hammarström, A., Hogstedt, C., Marteinsdóttir, I., ... & Hall, C. (2017). A systematic review including meta-analysis of work environment and burnout symptoms. *BMC public health*, 17(1), 264. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-017-4153-7>

Aylmer, R. & Dias, M. (2018). Are the generational interactions in the Brazilian workplace different from other countries? *Global Journal of Human Resource Management*, 6(1), 9-25.

Aylmer, R. (2010) *Negociação e liderança: o papel da chefia direta na gestão da pressão / Roberto Aylmer*. Rio de Janeiro: Dissertação de Mestrado apresentada ao programa de pós-graduação da Escola Brasileira de Administração Pública de Empresas da Fundação Getúlio Vargas, 183 pp.

- Aylmer, R. (2019) *The Socialization Process in a Brazilian State-Owned Company*. Doctoral Thesis: Rennes School of Business, France.
- Baker, C., Wuest, J., & Stern, P.N. (1992). Method slurring the grounded theory - phenomenology example. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 17(11), 1355–1360. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2648.2000.01430.x>
- Bartholow, B. D., Fabiani, M., Gratton, G., & Bettencourt, B. A. (2001). A psychophysiological examination of cognitive processing of and affective responses to social expectancy violations. *Psychological science*, 12(3), 197-204. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9280.00336>
- Bauer, T. N., & Erdogan, B. (2011). Organizational socialization: The effective onboarding of new employees. In S. Zedeck (Ed.), *APA handbook of industrial and organizational psychology* (Vol. 3: Maintaining, expanding, and contracting the organization, APA Handbooks in Psychology, pp. 51–64). Washington, DC, USA: American Psychological Association.
- Bauer, T. N., & Green, S. G. (1998). Testing the combined effects of newcomer information seeking and manager behavior on socialization. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 83, 72–83. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.83.1.72>
- Bauer, T. N., & Truxillo, D. M. (2000). Temp-to-permanent employees: A longitudinal study of stress and selection success. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 5, 337–346. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/1076-8998.5.3.337>
- Bauer, T. N., Bodner, T., Erdogan, B., Truxillo, D. M., & Tucker, J. S. (2007). Newcomer adjustment during organizational socialization: A meta-analytic review of antecedents, outcomes, and methods. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 92, 707–721. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.92.3.707>
- Bauer, T. N., Morrison, E. W., & Callister, R. R. (1998). Organizational socialization: A review and directions for future research. In G. R. Ferris (Ed.), *Research in personnel and human resources management* (Vol. 16, pp. 149–214). Stamford, CT: JAI Press.
- Becker, H. S. (1960). Notes on the concept of commitment. *American journal of Benson Sociology*, 66(1), 32-40. <https://doi.org/10.1086/222820>
- Berg, B. L. (2001). *Qualitative Research Methods for the Social Sciences*, ed. by Allyn and Bacon.
- Berger, P. L., & Luckmann, T. (1967) *The social construction oi reality*. New York: Doubleday.
- Bettencourt, B.A., Dill, K.E., Greathouse, S., Charlton, K., & Mulholland, A. (1997). Predicting evaluations of ingroup and outgroup members: The role of category-based expectancy violation. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 33, 244–275. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1006/jesp.1996.1323>
- Bettencourt, B.A., Eubanks, J., & Ernst, J. (1999). *Affective response to category-based expectancy violations*. Manuscript submitted for publication.
- Black, J. S., & Ashford, S. J. (1995). Fitting in or making jobs fit: Factors affecting mode of adjustment for new hires. *Human Relations*, 48, 421–437. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001872679504800407>
- Blau, P. M. (1964). *Exchange and power in social life*. New York, NY: Wiley
- Blumer, H. (1969) *Symbolic interactionism: Perspectives and method*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Blumer, H. (1986). *Symbolic interactionism: Perspective and method*. University of California Press.
- Burgoon, J. K. (1978). A communication model of personal space violations: Explication and an initial test. *Human Communication Research*, 4(2), 129-142. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2958.1978.tb00603.x>
- Burgoon, J.K. (1993). Interpersonal expectations, expectancy violations, and emotional communication. *Journal of Language and Social Psychology*, 12, 30–48. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0261927X93121003>
- Burgoon, J. K., & Walther, J. B. (1990). Nonverbal expectancies and the evaluative consequences of violations. *Human Communication Research*, 17(2), 232-265.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2958.1990.tb00232.x>

Burgoon, J. K., Berger, C. R., & Waldron, V. R. (2000). Mindfulness and interpersonal communication. *Journal of Social Issues*, 56(1), 105–127. <https://doi.org/10.1111/0022-4537.00154>

Burgoon, J. K., Manusov, V., Mineo, P., & Hale, J. L. (1985). Effects of eye gaze on hiring, credibility, attraction and relational message interpretation. *Journal of Nonverbal Behavior*, 9, 133–146. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/BF01000735>

Dias, M. (2016). *Business Negotiations in the Brazilian Culture* (Doctoral Thesis). Rennes School of Business, France. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18660.22407>

Cable, D.M., & Parsons, C.K. (2001). Socialization tactics and person-organization fit. *Personnel Psychology*, 54, 1–23. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.17446570.2001.tb00083.x>

Carter, M. J., & Fuller, C. (2015). Symbolic interactionism. *Sociopedia. isa*, 1, 1-17. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/205684601561>

Cascio, W. F., & Aguinis, H. (2008). 3 Staffing Twenty-first-century Organizations. *The Academy of Management Annals*, 2(1), 133-165. <https://doi.org/10.5465/19416520802211461>

Chatman, J.A. (1991). Matching people and organizations: Selection and socialization in public accounting firms. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 36, 459–484. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2393204>

Chen, G. (2005). Newcomer adaptation in teams: Multilevel antecedents and outcomes. *Academy of Management Journal*, 48, 101–116. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5465/AMJ.2005.15993147>

Chen, G., & Klimoski, R. J. (2003). The impact of expectations on newcomer performance in teams as mediated by work characteristics, social exchange, and empowerment. *Academy of Management Journal*, 46, 591–607. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/30040651>

Coleman, J. S. (1988). Social capital in the creation of human capital. *American journal of sociology*, 94, S95-S120.

Collinson, D. L., & Collinson, M. (1997). Delaying managers, time- space surveillance and its gendered effects. *Organization*, 4(3), 373–405. <https://doi.org/10.1177/135050849743005>

Conway, N., & Briner, R. B. (2005). *Understanding psychological contracts at work: A critical evaluation of theory and research*. Oxford University Press.

Conway, N., & Coyle-Shapiro, J. A.-M. (2012). The reciprocal relationship between psychological contract fulfilment and employee performance and the moderating role of perceived organizational support and tenure. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 85, 277–299. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8325.2011.02033.x>

Corley, K. & Gioia, D. (2011). Building theory about theory building: What Constitutes a Theoretical Contribution? *Academy of Management Review*, 36(1), 12–32. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.2009.0486>

Coyle-Shapiro, J. A., & Conway, N. (2004). *The employment relationship through the lens of social exchange*.

Coyle-Shapiro, J. A., & Conway, N. (2005). Exchange relationships: Examining psychological contracts and perceived organizational support. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 90, 774–781. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.90.4.774>

Coyle-Shapiro, J., & Kessler, I. (2000). Consequences of the psychological contract for the employment relationship: A large scale survey. *Journal of management studies*, 37(7), 903–930. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-6486.00210>

Cropanzano, R., & Mitchell, M. S. (2005). Social Exchange Theory: An Interdisciplinary Review. *Journal of Management*, 31, 874-900. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0149206305279602>

Cropanzano, R., Howes, J. C., Grandey, A. A., & Toth, P. (1997). The relationship of organizational politics and support to work behaviors, attitudes, and stress. *Journal of*

- Organizational behavior*, 18(2), 159-180. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICD\)1099-1379\(199703\)18:2%3C159::AID-JOB795%3E3.0.CO;2-D](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICD)1099-1379(199703)18:2%3C159::AID-JOB795%3E3.0.CO;2-D)
- Cruz, B.S. & Dias, M. (2020). COVID-19: from Outbreak to Pandemic. *Global Scientific Journals*, 8(3), 22302238.
- Dabos, G. E., & Rousseau, D. M. (2004, August). Social interaction patterns shaping employee psychological contracts. In *Academy of Management Proceedings* (Vol. 2004, No. 1, pp. N1-N6). Briarcliff Manor, NY 10510: Academy of Management.
- De Vos, A., Buyens, D., & Schalk, R. (2003). Psychological contract development during organization socialization: Adaptation to reality and the role of reciprocity. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 24, 537-559. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.205>
- Delobbe, N., Cooper-Thomas, H. D., & De Hoe, R. (2016). A new look at the psychological contract during organizational socialization: The role of newcomers' obligations at entry. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 37(6), 845-867. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.2078>
- Delorme, M. (2007). *Les compétences stratégiques des dirigeants: application au cas des entreprises canadiennes de biotechnologie*. Thèse de doctorat, Université Robert Schuman (Strasbourg 3).
- Devendorf, S. A., & Highhouse, S. (2008). Applicant-employee similarity and attraction to an employer. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 81(4), 607-617. <https://doi.org/10.1348/096317907X248842>
- Dias, M. (2018). Theoretical Approaches on Trust in Business Negotiations. *Saudi Journal of Business and Management Studies*, 3(11), 1228-1234. <https://doi.org/10.21276/sjbms.2018.3.11.5>
- Dias, M. (2020) The Four-Type Negotiation Matrix: A Model for Assessing Negotiation Processes. *British Journal of Education*, 8(5), 40-57. <https://doi.org/10.37745/bje/vol8.no5.p40-57.2020>
- Dias, M. et al. (2015). Brazilian Fashion Business Dudalina S/A: Case Revisited. *International Journal of Business and Management Studies*, 4(1), 11-24. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7834730>
- Dias, M. Navarro, R. (2020). Three-Strategy Level Negotiation Model and Four-Type Negotiation Matrix Applied to Brazilian Government Negotiation Cases. *British Journal of Management and Marketing Studies*, 3(3), 50-66. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.12479861>
- Dias, M., (2016). *Factors Influencing the Success of Business Negotiations in the Brazilian Culture* (Doctoral Thesis). Rennes School of Business, France. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18660.22407>
- Dias, M.D., Teles, A.C., Lafraia, J., & Pereira, L.J. (2023). Show Me Your Hands: A Moderator Effect Analysis on Nonverbal Behavior at the Bargaining Table. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 1(2), 119-127. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(2\).12](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(2).12)
- Dias, M. de O., Lafraia, J., Schmitz, T., & Vieira, P. (2023). Systematic Literature Review on Negotiation & Conflict Management. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 1(3), 20-31. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(3\).03](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(3).03)
- Dias, M., Fernandes, B., Quintão, H., Coelho, G., Boros, C. (2022) How Does the Violation of Trust Influence Project Management Negotiations? *Research and Analysis Journal*, 5(8), 17-26. <https://doi.org/10.18535/raj.v5i8.313>
- Dias, M., Lopes, R. (2020) Will the COVID-19 Pandemic Reshape our Society? *EAS Journal of Humanities and Cultural Studies (EAS J Humanit Cult Stud)* 6(2), 93-97. <https://doi.org/10.36349/EASJHCS.2020.V02I02.013>
- Dias, M., & Navarro, R. (2018). Is Netflix Dominating Brazil? *International Journal of Business and Management Review*, 6(1), 19-32.
- Dias, M., Navarro, R. & Valle, A. (2013). BMW and Brazilian Federal Government: Enhancing the Automotive Industry Regulatory Environment. *International Journal of Arts and Sciences*, 6(2), 551-567. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7834742>
- Dias, M., Pereira, L; Vieira, P., & Pan, Juliana (2022) From Plato to e-Leaders: The Evolution

of Leadership Theories and Styles. *Economics and Business Quarterly Reviews*, 5(2), 133-146, <https://doi.org/10.31014/aior.1992.05.02.420>

Dias, M., Teles, A. & Duzert, Y. (2018) Did Embraer Succeed In Adopting The International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) In Brazil? *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 6(2), 51-62.

Dias, M., Teles, A., Duzert, Y. (2018) Will Boeing Succeed with the Embraer Acquisition Operation, Despite the Brazilian Federal Government Golden Share Veto? *International Journal of Business and Management Review*, 6(2), 55-64.

<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7834718>

Dias, M.; (2018). Seven supportive Theories on Negotiation. *Global Journal of Research Analysis*, 7(11), 493-494.

<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7834349>

Dias, M. & Duzert, Y. (2019). Teaching Materials: Role Play Simulation on Romantic Involvement In The Workplace. *International Journal of Management, Technology and Engineering*, 9(1), 124-133.

<https://doi.org/16.10089/IJMTE.2019.V9I01.18.27418>

Dias, M., Duzert, Y. & Teles, A. (2018). Boeing, Brazilian Federal Government, And Embraer: Golden Share Veto and The Anatomy of a Joint Venture. *International Journal of Business and Management Studies*, 7(2), 71-80.

<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14972.18563>

Dias, M.; Krein, J.; Streh, E.; Vilhena, J. B. (2018) Agriculture Cooperatives in Brazil: Cotribá Case. *International Journal of Management, Technology and Engineering*, 8(12).

<https://doi.org/16.10089/IJMTE.2018.V8I12.17.2243>

Dias, M. & Lopes, R. (2019). Role Play Simulation on Farm Debt: Brazilian Case. *SSRG International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 6(4), 84-93.

<https://doi.org/10.112/gsj.2019.08.26384>

Dias, M. & Lopes, R. (2019). Teaching Materials: Role Play Simulation on Small Business Debt Collection in Brazil. *International Journal of*

Management, Technology and Engineering, 9(8), 237-249.

<https://doi.org/16.10089/IJMTE.2019.V9I8.19.29127>

Dulac, T., Coyle-Shapiro, J. A.-M., Henderson, D. J., & Wayne, S. J. (2008). Not all responses to breach are the same: A longitudinal study examining the interconnection of social exchange and psychological contract processes in organizations. *Academy of Management Journal*, 51(6).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.5465/AMJ.2008.35732596>

Eisenberger, R., & Stinglhamber, F. (2011). Perceived organizational support: Fostering enthusiastic and productive employees. *American Psychological Association*.

<https://doi.org/10.1037/12318-000>

Eisenberger, R., Huntington, R., Hutchison, S., & Sowa, D. (1986). Perceived organizational support. *Journal of Applied psychology*, 71(3), 500.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.71.3.500>

Eisenberger, R., Stinglhamber, F., Vandenberghe, C., Sucharski, I. L., & Rhoades, L. (2002). Perceived supervisor support: Contributions to perceived organizational support and employee retention. *Journal of applied psychology*, 87(3), 565.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1037//0021-9010.87.3.565>

Farmer, S. M., Van Dyne, L., & Kamdar, D. (2015). The contextualized self: How team-member exchange leads to coworker identification and helping OCB. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 100(2), 583.

<https://doi.org/10.1037/a0037660>

Fiorotti, K. P., Rossoni, R. R., Borges, L. H., & Miranda, A. E. (2010). Common mental disorders in medical students: Prevalence and associated factors. *Jornal Brasileiro de Psiquiatria*, 59(1), 17-23.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/S0047-20852010000100003>

George, J. M., Reed, T. F., Ballard, K. A., Colin, J., & Fielding, J. (1993). Contact with AIDS patients as a source of work-related distress: Effects of organizational and social support. *Academy of Management Journal*, 36(1), 157-171.

- Gioia, D. A., & Pitre, E. (1990). Multiparadigm perspectives on theory building. *Academy of management review*, 15(4), 584-602. <https://doi.org/10.2307/258683>
- Gioia, D. A., Corley, K. G., & Fabbri, T. (2002). Revising the past (while thinking in the future perfect tense). *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 15(6), 622-634. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/09534810210449532>
- Gioia, D. A., Corley, K. G., & Hamilton, A. L. (2013). Seeking qualitative rigor in inductive research: Notes on the Gioia methodology. *Organizational research methods*, 16(1), 15-31. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/1094428112452151>
- Glaser, B. G. (2001). *The grounded theory perspective: Conceptualization contrasted with description*. Sociology Press.
- Glaser, B., & Strauss, A. (1967). *The Discovery of Grounded Theory: Strategies for Qualitative Research*. Mill Valley, CA: Sociology Press.
- Goldberg, D. P., & Huxley, P. (1992). *Common mental disorders: A bio-social model*. New York, NY, US: Tavistock/Routledge.
- Goldberg, D., & Goodyer, I. M. (2014). *The origins and course of common mental disorders*. Routledge.
- Gouldner, A. W. (1960). *The norm of reciprocity: A preliminary statement*. New York: John Wiley.
- Graen, G. B., & Scandura, T. A. (1987). Toward a psychology of dyadic organizing. *Research in organizational behavior*, 9, 175-208.
- Graen, G. B., & Uhl-Bien, M. (1995). Relationship-based approach to leadership: Development of leader-member exchange (LMX) theory of leadership over 25 years: Applying a multi-level multi-domain perspective. *The leadership quarterly*, 6(2), 219-247. [https://doi.org/10.1016/1048-9843\(95\)90036-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/1048-9843(95)90036-5)
- Hamilton, D. L., & Trolier, T. K. (1986). Stereotypes and stereotyping: An overview of the cognitive approach. *Psychology*.
- Handberg, C., Thorne, S., Midtgaard, J., Nielsen, C. V., & Lomborg, K. (2015). Revisiting symbolic interactionism as a theoretical framework beyond the grounded theory tradition. *Qualitative health research*, 25(8), 1023-1032. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732314554231>
- Henderson, D. J., Wayne, S. J., Shore, L. M., Bomme, W. H., & Tetrick, L. E. (2008). Leader-member exchange, differentiation, and psychological contract fulfillment: A multilevel examination. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 93, 1208-1219. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0012678>
- Hiltrop, J. M. (1996). Managing the changing psychological contract. *Employee relations*, 18(1), 36-49. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01425459610110227>
- Homans, G. (1961). *Social behavior: Its elementary forms*. New York, NY: Harcourt Brace.
- Homans, G. C. (1958). Social behavior as exchange. *American journal of sociology*, 63(6), 597-606. <https://doi.org/10.1086/222355>
- Howe, N., & Strauss, W. (2007). *Millennials go to college* (2nd ed.). Great Falls, VA: Life Course Associates.
- Jackson, L.A., Sullivan, L.A., & Hodge, C.N. (1993). Stereotype effects on attributions, predictions, and evaluations: No two social judgments are quite alike. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 65, 69-84.
- Jokisaari, M., & Nurmi, J. E. (2009). Change in newcomers' supervisor support and socialization outcomes after organizational entry. *Academy of Management Journal*, 52, 527-544. <https://doi.org/10.5465/AMJ.2009.41330971>
- Jones, E. E. (1990). *Interpersonal perception*. WH Freeman/Times Books/Henry Holt & Co.
- Jones, G. R. (1986). Socialization tactics, self-efficacy, and newcomers' adjustments to organizations. *Academy of Management Journal*, 29, 262-279. <https://doi.org/10.2307/256188>
- Kammeyer-Mueller, J. D., & Wanberg, C. R. (2003). Unwrapping the organizational entry process: disentangling multiple antecedents and their pathways to adjustment. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 88(5), 779. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.88.5.779>

- Kammeyer-Mueller, J., Wanberg, C., Rubenstein, A., & Song, Z. (2013). Support, undermining, and newcomer socialization: Fitting in during the first 90 days. *Academy of Management Journal*, 56, 1104–1124. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5465/amj.2010.0791>
- Katz, R. (1978a) Job longevity as a situational factor in job satisfaction. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 23, 204-223. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2392562>
- Katz, R. (1978b) The influence of job longevity on employee reactions to task characteristics. *Human Relations*, 31, 703-725. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001872677803100804>
- Katz, R. (1980) Time and work: Toward an integrative perspective. In B. M. Staw & L. L. Cummings (Eds.), *Research organizational behavior* (Vol. 2, pp. 81-127). Greenwich, CT: IAI Press.
- Katz, R., & Tushman, M. (1983) A longitudinal study of the effects of boundary spanning supervision on turnover and promotion in research and development. *Academy of Management Journal*, 26, 437-456. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/256255>
- Kelley, H. H., & Thibaut, J. W. (1969). Group problem solving. *The handbook of social psychology*, 4, 1-101.
- Khazanchi, S., & Masterson, S. S. (2011). Who and what is fair matters: A multi-foci social exchange model of creativity? *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 32(1), 86-106. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/job.682>
- Kim, T., Cable, D. M., & Kim, S. (2005). Socialization tactics, employee proactivity, and person– organization fit. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 90, 232–241. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.90.2.232>
- Leets, L. (2001). Responses to internet hate sites: Is speech too free in cyberspace? *Communication Law & Policy*, 6(2), 287-317. http://dx.doi.org/10.1207/S15326926CLP0602_2
- Dias & Navarro (2018) Four-Level Negotiation Model and Four-Type Negotiation Matrix Applied to Brazilian Government Negotiation Cases. *British Journal of Management and Marketing Studies*, 3(3), 50-66. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.12479861>
- Levinson, C. A., Lipkin, H. J., & Meshkov, S. (1963). *Phys. Letters* 1, 44.
- Levinson, H. (1965). Reciprocation: The relationship between man and organization. *Administrative science quarterly*, 370-390. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2391032>
- Levinson, H., Price, C. R., Munden, K. J., Mandl, H. J., & Solley, C. M. (1962). Men, management, and mental health.
- Liden, R. C., Bauer, T. N., & Erdogan, B. (2004). The role of leader-member exchange in the dynamic relationship between employer and employee: Implications for employee socialization, leaders, and organizations. *The employment relationship: Examining psychological and contextual perspectives*, 226-250.
- Liu, S., Wang, M., Bamberger, P., Shi, J., & Bacharach, S. B. (2015). The dark side of socialization: A longitudinal investigation of newcomer alcohol use. *Academy of Management Journal*, 58(2), 334-355. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5465/amj.2013.0239>
- Madlock, P. E. 2008. The link between leadership style, communicator competence, and employee satisfaction. *Journal of Business Communication*, 45(1), 61-78. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5465/amj.2013.0239>
- Major, D. A., Kozlowski, S. W. J., Chao, G. T., & Gardner, P. D. (1994). A longitudinal investigation of newcomer expectations, early socialization outcomes, and the moderating effects. *Management Studies*, 7(2), 71–80. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.80.3.418>
- Mandler, G. (1990). A constructivist theory of emotion. In N.S. Stein, B.L. Leventhal, & T. Trabasso (Eds.), *Psychological and biological approaches to emotion* (pp. 21–43).
- Marston, C. (2007). *Motivating the “What’s in it for me?” workforce: Manage across the generational divide and increase profits*. Hoboken: Wiley.
- Masterson, S. S., Lewis, K., Goldman, B. M., & Taylor, M. S. (2000). Integrating justice and social exchange: The differing effects of fair

work procedures and treatment on work relationships. *Academy of Management Journal*, 43, 738–748. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/1556364>

Menninger, K. (1958). Theory of psychoanalytic technique.

Meyer, J. P., & Allen, N. J. (1984). Testing the "side-bet theory" of organizational commitment: Some methodological considerations. *Journal of applied psychology*, 69(3), 372. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037//0021-9010.69.3.372>

Meyer, J. P., & Allen, N. J. (1991). A three-component conceptualization of organizational commitment. *Human resource management review*, 1(1), 61-89. [https://doi.org/10.1016/1053-4822\(91\)90011-Z](https://doi.org/10.1016/1053-4822(91)90011-Z)

Meyer, J. P., & Parfyonova, N. M. (2010). Normative commitment in the workplace: A theoretical analysis and re-conceptualization. *Human resource management review*, 20(4), 283-294. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmmr.2009.09.001>

Meyer, J. P., Allen, N. J., & Gellatly, I. R. (1990). Affective and continuance commitment to the organization: Evaluation of measures and analysis of concurrent and time-lagged relations. *Journal of applied psychology*, 75(6), 710. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.75.6.710>

Meyer, J. P., Allen, N. J., & Smith, C. A. (1993). Commitment to organizations and occupations: Extension and test of a three-component conceptualization. *Journal of applied psychology*, 78(4), 538. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.78.4.538>

Meyer, J. P., Becker, T. E., & Van Dick, R. (2006). Social identities and commitments at work: Toward an integrative model. *Journal of Organizational Behavior: The International Journal of Industrial, Occupational and Organizational Psychology and Behavior*, 27(5), 665-683. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.383>

Meyer, J. P., Srinivas, E. S., Lal, J. B., & Topolnytsky, L. (2007). Employee commitment and support for an organizational change: Test of the three-component model in two cultures. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*,

80(2), 185-211. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1348/096317906X118685>

Meyer, J. P., Stanley, D. J., Herscovitch, L., & Topolnytsky, L. (2002). Affective, continuance, and normative commitment to the organization: A meta-analysis of antecedents, correlates, and consequences. *Journal of vocational behavior*, 61(1), 20-52. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jvbe.2001.1842>

Miles, M. & Huberman, A. (1994). *Qualitative Data Analysis*. 2nd edition. London: Sage.

Miles, M., Huberman, A. & Saldaña, J. (2014). *Qualitative Data Analysis: a Methods Sourcebook*. 3rd edition. London: Sage.

Mintzberg, H. (2005). Developing theory about the development of theory. Great minds in management: *The process of theory development*, 355-372.

Mitchell, R. K., Agle, B. R., & Wood, D. J. (1997). Toward a theory of stakeholder identification and salience: Defining the principle of who and what really counts. *Academy of Management Review*, 22, 853–886. <https://doi.org/10.2307/259247>

Mohamed, A. A., Orife, J. N., & Slack, F. J. (2001). Organizational reputation: A literature review and a model. *International Journal of Management*, 18(2), 260-260. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0149206310390963>

Moideenkutty, U., Blau, G., Kumar, R. & Nalakath, A. (2001). Perceived Organizational Support as a Mediator of the Relationship of Perceived Situational Factors to Affective Organizational Commitment. *Applied Psychology: An International Review*, 40(4), 615-634. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/1464-0597.00076>

Moreland, R. L., & Levine, J. M. (1982). Group socialization: Temporal changes in individual-group relations. In L. Berkowitz (Ed.), *Advances in experimental social psychology* (Vol. 15, pp. 137–192). New York: Academic Press.

Moreland, R. L., & Levine, J. M. (2001). Socialization in organizations and work groups. In M. E. Turner (Ed.), *Groups at work: Theories and research* (pp. 69–112). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.

- Mowday, R. T., Steers, R. M., & Porter, L. W. (1979). The measurement of organizational commitment. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 14, 224–247. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0001-8791\(79\)90072-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0001-8791(79)90072-1)
- Mowday, R., Steers, R., & Porter, L. (1982). *Employee-Organization Linkages: The Psychology of Commitment, Absenteeism, and Turnover*. New York, NY: Academic Press.
- Myers M. D., & Newman, M. (2007). The qualitative interview in IS research: Examining the craft. *Information and Organization*, 17(1), 2-26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infoandorg.2006.11.001>
- Myers, K. K., & Oetzel, J. G. (2003). Exploring the dimensions of organizational assimilation: Creating and validating a measure. *Communication Quarterly*, 51, 438–457. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/01463370309370166>
- Myers, K. K., & Sadaghiani, K. (2010). Millennial in the work-place: A communication perspective on Millennials' organizational relationships and performance. *Journal of Business Psychology*, 25, 225-238. <https://doi.org/10.1007%2Fs10869-010-9172-7>
- Myers, M. D. (2008). *Qualitative Research in Information Systems, updated version*. MIS Quarterly.
- Olson, J.M., Roese, N.J., & Zanna, M.P. (1996). *Expectancies*. In E.T. Higgins & A.W.
- Ostroff, C., & Kozlowski, S. W. (1992). Organizational socialization as a learning process: The role of information acquisition. *Personnel Psychology*, 45, 849–874. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6570.1992.tb00971.x>
- Ostroff, C., & Kozlowski, S. W. (1993). The role of mentoring in the information gathering processes of newcomers during early organizational socialization. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 42, 170–183. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jvbe.1993.1012>
- Parker, S. K. (1998). Enhancing role breadth self-efficacy: The roles of job enrichment and other organizational interventions. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 83, 835–852. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.83.6.835>
- Parzefall, M. R. (2008). Psychological contracts and reciprocity: A study in a Finnish context. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 19(9), 1703-1719. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585190802295272>
- Payne, S. C., Culbertson, S. S., Boswell, W. R., & Barger, E. J. (2008). Newcomer psychological contracts and employee socialization activities: Does perceived balance in obligations matter? *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 73(3), 465-472. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2008.09.003>
- Persell, C. (1990). Becoming a member of society through socialization. *Understanding Society: An Introduction to Sociology*, 98-107.
- Petrobras (2017). Oil Production in Brazil from 1980 – 2020. Retrieved from <http://www.investidorpetrobras.com.br/en/operational-highlights/production-and-marketing>
- Petrobras (2018). Evolution of Petrobras System's Staff. Retrieved from <http://www.petrobras.com.br/en/about-us/careers/>
- Porter, L. W., Lawler, E. E., & Hackman, J. R. (1975). *Behavior in organizations*.
- Porter, L. W., Steers, R. M., Mowday, R. T., & Boulian, P. (1974). Organizational commitment, job satisfaction and turnover among psychiatric technicians. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 59, 603-609. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/h0037335>
- Raines, C. (2002). *Connecting generations: The sourcebook for a new workplace*. Berkeley, CA: Crisp Publications.
- Rousseau, D. M. (1989). Psychological and implicit contracts in organizations. *Employee Responsibilities and Rights Journal*, 2, 121–139. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/BF01384942>
- Rousseau, D. M. (1990). New hire perceptions of their own and employer's obligations: A study of psychological contracts. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 11, 389–400. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.4030110506>

- Rousseau, D. M. (1995). *Psychological contracts in organizations. Understanding written and unwritten agreements*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Rousseau, D. M. (2001). Schema promise and mutuality: The building blocks of the psychological contracts. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 74, 511–541. <https://doi.org/10.1348/096317901167505>
- Rousseau, D. M. (2004). Psychological contracts in the workplace: Understanding the ties that motivate. *Academy of Management Executive*, 18, 120–127. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5465/AME.2004.12689213>
- Rousseau, D. M., & McLean Parks, J. (1993). The contracts of individuals and organizations. *Research in Organizational behavior*, 15, 1-1.
- Rupp, D. E., & Cropanzano, R. (2002). The mediating effects of social exchange relationships in predicting workplace outcomes from multifoci organizational justice. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 89, 925–946. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0749-5978\(02\)00036-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0749-5978(02)00036-5)
- Sadaghiani, K., & Myers, K. K. (2009). *Parents' influence on leadership values: The vocational anticipatory socialization of young millennial adults*. Paper presented at the Western States Communication Association 80th Annual Convention, Mesa, AZ.
- Saks, A. M., & Ashforth, B. E. (1997). Organizational socialization: Making sense of the past and present as a prologue for the future. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 51(2), 234-279. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jvbe.1997.1614>
- Saks, A. M., Uggerslev, K. L., & Fassina, N. E. (2007). Socialization tactics and newcomer adjustment: A meta-analytic review and test of a model. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 70, 413–446. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2006.12.004>
- Saldaña, J. (2013). *The coding manual for qualitative researchers*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A. (2009). *Research Methods for Business Students*. Harlow, England: Prentice Hall, 5th edition.
- Schein, E. H. (1968). Organizational socialization and the profession of management. *Industrial Management Review*, 9, 1–16.
- Scott, C. W., & Myers, K. K. (2010). Toward an integrative theoretical perspective of membership negotiations: Socialization, assimilation, and the duality of structure. *Communication Theory*, 30, 79–105. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2885.2009.01355.x>
- Seers, A. (1989). Team-member exchange quality: A new construct for role-making research. *Organizational behavior and human decision processes*, 43(1), 118-135. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(89\)90060-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(89)90060-5)
- Settoon, R. P., Bennett, N., & Liden, R. C. (1996). Social exchange in organizations: Perceived organizational support, leader-member exchange, and employee reciprocity. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 81, 219–227. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.81.3.219>
- Shore, L. M., & Shore, T. H. (1995). Perceived organizational support and organizational justice. *Organizational politics, justice, and support: Managing the social climate of the workplace*, 149, 164.
- Shore, L. M., & Tetrick, L. E. (1994). The psychological contract as an explanatory framework'. *Trends in organizational behavior*, 1, 91-109.
- Shore, L. M., Barksdale, K., & Shore, T. H. (1995). Managerial perceptions of employee commitment to the organization. *Academy of Management journal*, 38(6), 1593-1615. <https://doi.org/10.2307/256845>
- Shore, L.M., & Tetrick, L.E. (1991). A construct validity study of the survey of perceived organizational support. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 76, 637-643. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.76.5.637>
- Sluss, D. M., & Ashforth, B. E. (2007). Relational identity and identification: Defining ourselves through work relationships. *Academy of*

Management Review, 32, 9–32.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.5465/AMR.2007.23463672>

Sluss, D. M., & Thompson, B. S. (2012). Socializing the newcomer: The mediating role of leader–member exchange. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 119(1), 114–125.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.obhdp.2012.05.005>

Smith, C. A., Organ, D. W., & Near, J. P. (1983). Organizational citizenship behavior: Its nature and antecedents. *Journal of applied psychology*, 68(4), 653.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.68.4.653>

Smith, P. S. (1978). *Petróleo e política no Brasil moderno*. Rio de Janeiro: Artenova.

Smola, K., & Sutton, C. (2002). Generational Differences: Revisiting Generational Work Values for the New Millennium. *Journal of Organizational Behaviour*, 23(4), 363–382.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/job.147>

Song, L., Tsui, A. S., & Law, K. S. (2009). Unpacking employee responses to organizational exchange mechanisms: The role of social and economic exchange perceptions. *Journal of Management*, 35(1), 56–93.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206308321544>

Sparrowe, R. T., & Liden, R. C. (1997). Process and structure in leader-member exchange. *Academy of management Review*, 22(2), 522–552.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/259332>

Taylor, M. S., & Tekleab, A. G. (2004). Taking stock of psychological contract research: Assessing progress, addressing troublesome issues, and setting research priorities. In J. A.-M. Coyle-Shapiro, L. M. Shore, M. S. Taylor, & L. E. Tetrick (Eds.), *The employment relationship. Examining psychological and contextual perspectives* (pp. 253–283). Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.

Tekleab, A. G. (2003). *The role of realistic job previews and organizational socialization on newcomers' psychological contract development* (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). University of Maryland, College Park, MD.

Tekleab, A. G., & Chiaburu, D. S. (2011). Social exchange: Empirical examination of form and

focus. *Journal of Business Research*, 64, 460–466.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2010.03.005>

Thibaut, J. W. & Kelley, HH (1959). The social psychology of groups.

Tierney, P., Farmer, S. M., & Graen, G. B. (1999). An examination of leadership and employee creativity: The relevance of traits and relationships. *Personnel psychology*, 52(3), 591–620.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6570.1999.tb00173.x>

Van Dick, R., van Knippenberg, D., Kerschreiter, R., Hertel, G., & Wieseke, J. (2008). Interactive effects of work group and organizational identification on job satisfaction and extra-role behavior. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 72, 388–399.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2007.11.009>

Van Dyne, L., Graham, J. W., & Dienesch, R. M. (1994). Organizational citizenship behavior: Construct redefinition, measurement, and validation. *Academy of management Journal*, 37(4), 765–802. <https://doi.org/10.2307/256600>

Van Knippenberg, D., & Schie, E. (2000). Foci and correlates of organizational identification. *Journal of occupational and organizational psychology*, 73(2), 137–147.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1348/096317900166949>

Van Maanen, J., & Schein, E. (1979). Toward a theory of organizational socialization. *Research in Organizational Behavior*, 1, 209–264.

Wanberg, C. R., & Kammeyer-Mueller, J. D. (2000) Predictors And Outcomes Of Proactivity In The Socialization Process. *Journal Of Applied Psychology*, 85(3), 373–385.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1037//0021-9010.85.3.373>

Wang, M., Kammeyer-Mueller, J., Liu, et al. (2015). Context, socialization, and newcomer learning. *Organizational Psychology Review*, 5, 3–25.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/2041386614528832>

Wang, M., Zhan, Y., McCune, E., & Truxillo, D. (2011). Understanding newcomers' adaptability and work-related outcomes: Testing the mediating roles of perceived P-E fit variables. *Personnel Psychology*, 64, 163–189.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6570.2010.01205.x>

Wanous, J. P. (1992). *Organizational entry: Recruitment, selection, orientation, and socialization of newcomers*. Reading, MA: Addison- Wesley.

Wayne, S. J., Shore, L. M., & Liden, R. C. (1997). Perceived organizational support and leader-member exchange: A social exchange

perspective. *Academy of Management Journal*, 40(1), 82-111. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/257021>

WHO (2024) *WHO releases new International Classification of Diseases (ICD 11)* Retrieved from [https://www.who.int/news-room/detail/18-06-2018-who-releases-new-international-classification-of-diseases-\(icd-11\)](https://www.who.int/news-room/detail/18-06-2018-who-releases-new-international-classification-of-diseases-(icd-11))